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Open Content Development in Engineering Education and Teacher Training

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ABSTRACT

The Open Content Development (OCD) model is intended to result in new content development of teaching methods and their implementation in practice. We aim to develop open – with active teacher/student contribution – content and to apply those contents in practice. The project, which was launched in 2016 with the support of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, is part of a complex subject pedagogical methodological innovation project. The aim is to provide the possibility of modernizing the materials in technical education continuously and rapidly and to raise the pupils/students' interest on the other. Serving the modernization of the subject named 'System Theory for All', our project aims to develop an innovative method, relying on the principle of open access, allows the students to do everyday development activities in framework system (Moodle). The project has offered the opportunity of cooperation in developing learning content, and school books, involving the lecturers and students (75 persons) into the construction works on various micro-content manageable online with the help of the method. As a result of our work, in the online teaching-learning space, which was created according to the up-to-date principles of network learning, the Sysbook electronic platform has been introduced as well as learning units (micro-content) elaborated by 265 students that have been made accessible in an up-to-date electronic archive and search system for a broader range of users. During the latest 18 months, our further training

program preparing the application of the process in a full professional circle has been attended by 110 VET teachers working in 12 VET institutions. In our paper, we introduce the model of open content development as an innovation process, the elaborated dynamic, interactive micro-content and the results gained during practical tests done with students.

1 INTRODUCTION

The openness in educational content has been one of the significant developments over the last two decades. While ensuring open access to the towers, the conceptual issue of our project is to open the development process to all participants. Students are now assisted by a large number of educational portals that make their open content accessible (W1) In the process of digital transformation, content development based on interactivity seems an innovative method. The training content development has stable didactical features [1] and is partly connected to the endeavours which strive to shape the alternatives of the traditional training curricula in a learning environment determined by new info-communication technology in the learning [2]. Concerning the new didactical model supported by digital transformation became an essential precondition of the online assessment of learning and innovation to be able to evaluate the methodological impacts of the system and to prove our preliminary working hypotheses on the broader professional base [3].

Developing Open Educational Resources (OER) with engineering students' participation means potential for improving the content. According to the new kind of students interactions [4], the channels and community-making elements of interpersonal communication have transformed (especially in the web 2.0 environment). As we introduced in our previous papers the open access to learning contents and Digital Pedagogy [5] has made a considerable try to renew pedagogical thinking after the millenary and firstly [6] at the universities. Nowadays, in content development, the rapidly changing elements determined by digital transformation aspects, and the dynamics of the changes are challenging to be forecasted [7].

Our concept covers the elaboration and introduction of a learning material modernization model created in an online environment within secondary and higher education in a collaborative way. Using this process, our aim, on the one hand, is to provide the possibility of modernizing the materials in technical education continuously and rapidly and to raise the pupils/students' interest on the other.

2 METHODS

One of the essential elements of our project is that engineer teacher training, conducted at two different faculties of our university, and electrical engineers' training has been connected in terms of thematic and methodological questions. The project

has offered the opportunity of cooperation in developing learning content and school books, involving the lecturers and students (75 persons) into the construction works on various micro-content manageable online with the help of the method. As a result of our work, in the online teaching-learning space, which was created according to the up-to-date principles of network learning, an electronic platform has been introduced as well as learning units (micro-content) elaborated by 265 students that have been made accessible in an up-to-date electronic archive and search system for a wider range of users. During the latest 18 months, our further training program preparing the application of the process in a wider professional circle has been attended by 110 VET teachers working in 12 VET institutions. In our lecture, we introduce the model of Open Content Development (OCD) as an innovation process, the elaborated dynamic interactive micro-content and the results gained during practical tests done with vocational teachers and engineer students.

Our first multi-levelled e-learning environment called *Sysbook* (W2) was included in our application. The constantly evolving *Sysbook* platform connects to the OCD model; this platform introduces the open learning resource elaborated about a certain comprehensive topic: About systems and management for everyone [8]. This platform (W3) presents the students' innovations, as well, and after an expert evaluation, the development results can be published here. In *Sysbook* several case studies show the application of system view. In the different examples it is investigated, what is considered a system, how is the system connected to its environment, what are the input signals and what are the output signals? How can the model of the system be built? What are the requirements set for the system? Which balance and energy considerations have to be applied? Can we control the system? How to control the system?

3 SUPPORTING FRAMEWORKS

We illustrate the implementation of our concept with three examples from the results of the project so far. *SysBook* has evolved from traditional engineering training and has provided an opportunity for methodological innovation. The *MC-HUNGLE* system provides explicit methodological support for micro-content developers. And creating a *MICROPEDIA* online platform will help you develop, archive, and deploy micro-content more widely.

3.1 SysBook

Considering the open approach, the students can contribute to the content of *Sysbook*. They can develop their contents related to systems and controls they are familiar with. After a review, this area can be supplemented with new materials. Till now, some examples are temperature control of a terrarium, speed control, model of the learning lab experiment, the model of motor, etc. (*Fig. 1*).

Fig. 1. Systems appearing in the Sysbook

Motivated computer engineering students created Java applet demonstrations in the field of control engineering during their summer internship programme at our university. These applets have been included in the “Control course” surface of *Sysbook*. Each applet is available both in English and in Hungarian, also linked with their PDF format instructions (Fig. 2.). The topics and demonstrations of the currently published applets are the following: Frequency analysis, Fourier analysis, Bode and Nyquist diagrams of a system, Shower temperature control, Juggler (inverted pendulum), continuous PID controller (series and parallel), discrete and continuous Youla controller, Prediction for first-order systems.

Fig. 2. Control Engineering Java applet demonstrations created by motivated students

Based on the OCD concept, we decided to design and develop a smartphone application which can help our students and teachers to reach our micro-content management systems. This decision was based both on the hypothesis of the research group and also on the current trends regarding the device usage in the Z

and Alpha generation students. The “Bring Your Own Device” (BYOD) phenomenon where the word “Device” can also be replaced with “Phone”, “Tablet”, “Personal Computer” etc. getting more and more popular in the different educational institutes from the primary schools to the universities. A self-developed application would help to strengthen this phenomenon and give more power into the hands of the users.

First, we made literature and market research concerning the different smartphone operating systems and marketplaces. From 2010 to the end of 2018, the dominance of Google’s Android operating system has grown from 20% to the currently 86% share of the market. 13% belongs to Apple’s iOS platform. The last 1% includes the other remaining systems [9]. Then, comparing the two platforms we decided to choose the Android platform for the first target as it is more open, the development is free, and no special devices are needed to develop applications. Our application is based on a WebView component, extending its features by different smartphone and Android-specific options, such as using pictures of the camera, different sensor data etc.

The source code of Sysbook was optimized for compact displays, and smaller screens as the current smartphones have (Fig. 3). We also enabled to run some JavaScript code snippets which are showing the expressions of the different words included in the glossary of Sysbook. We are currently working on an improvement of the application, applying the commonly used gestures (swiping, pull to refresh, etc.) instead of clicking on the different hyperlinks in Sysbook.

Fig. 3. Sysbook optimized for the smartphone application screen

In Sysbook there are four surfaces (levels): “Comics”, “What we are talking about”, “Control course” and “Mathematical representations, examples”. There are altogether almost 137 pages, in 11 different chapters. Two of the four surfaces can be shown on the screen, combining the left and right side also. "Comics" and "What we are talking about" levels are available for every page of Sysbook. These pages were written by academicians, professors and system experts for three target audience: to everybody; for different students, for the experts with different professions or the control specialists.

As the Sysbook is a base curriculum in different university subjects at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, the student might come from the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Informatics regarding the topic “Control Engineering”. Or the students also might come from the Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences regarding the subjects “System Theory for All” or “Digital Pedagogy”, usually engineering and economist teacher students. In the Student Area of Sysbook, the students can also design, create and publish their topics of interest as pages, micro-content in the area. After a peer review, these materials will also be available as part of the Sysbook.

3.2 MC-HUNGLE

Our second micro-content editing system called MC-HUNGLE can also be accessed using the smartphone application. MC HUNGLE is a LAMP-based (Linux, Apache HTTP Server, MySQL, PHP) Web 2.0 application, which can be opened using regular browsers or smartphone browsers also. The system is also used by the students of “Becoming an Engineer” at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Informatics and even by the partner institutes of our research group. This system is available currently only in Hungarian, but the internationalization of the interface is in progress. The main goal of the MC-HUNGLE system is to allow editing micro-contents with structured metadata supporting advanced search methods and explicit knowledge formalization. We designed our web application to offer the possibility to the quick and efficient elaboration of individual micro-contents without a high level of the mental load from users. As Fig. 4 shows content editor page is simplified, allowing authors to work focusing on knowledge allocation.

Fig. . Screenshot of content editor page from MC-HUNGLE

The title of the content unit should be expressive, concise, short. When creating a micro-content, we strive for clear, transparent communication. We can use an image or/and text block in the content unit. We suggest that an image should not be too

complicated; it should not contain much more detail than necessary understanding. The text block should have a maximum of 1024 characters; the content breakdown should aim for the introduction, the body and the conclusion. Entering tags and labels is very important for successful content mining. We recommend at least three or more labels to each micro-content. Authors can use one word or complex expression for a tag. It is essential to know that metadata of the original author of the content unit is retained even after reusing by other users (teachers, students).

Fig. 5. Different ways to organize and structure micro-contents by MC-HUNGLE (groups (basic set, thematic group and domain) and knowledge tracks)

Micro-contents can be represented as icons and thumbnail images. With a suitable algorithm, we generate and attach a unique colour code to individual content units. Over a certain number of items, it is necessary to organize micro-contents. There are two simple procedures. First one is to collect different content units into a higher level of groups (basic set, thematic group and domain). Elements for a topic are received by teachers and students, and this collection can be offered to others. There may be an array of similar topics, but users have the choice of the best ones for them, or they can reuse existing sets in whole or in part. The left side of *Fig. 5* shows these levels. The second one is selecting knowledge tracks on a large set of micro-contents. In this case, the teacher usually collects a lot of content units for a lesson or a course. In addition to this option, the teacher designates specific content units to be viewed in succession formed to one or more knowledge tracks. On the right side of Figure 5. these knowledge tracks are shown. There are three knowledge tracks marked with different colours altered lessons. Note that some micro-contents may participate in other knowledge tracks.

3.3 MICROPEDIA

The newest results of our survey have proved our hypothesis according to which one of the possible ways of increasing teacher activity is to offer, besides methodological support in learning the theoretically instant material in the increasingly accessible online learning environment, the possibility to join in the Learning Management Systems (LMS). The new micro contents, except for their different forms and topics, showed a significant potential for using them in the teachers' preparation for their lectures and practical work with students. Using the new set of micro contents 2018-2019 we established an archiving system for distributing the result of content development (W4), the next Fig. 6 shows a few screen pictures about the teachers' support portal:

Fig. 6. MICROPEDIA as a micro-content archiving system/portal (W4)

We integrated the MC-HUNGLE interface with our smartphone application (Fig. 7) where the users can create new micro-contents using the menu of the application, where for example they can attach a photo to a micro-content which was taken using the camera of the smartphone inside our app.

Fig. 7. MC HUNGLE micro-content editing system in the smartphone application and its menu

The third system is the newest one (available currently only in Hungarian), the OCD Micro-content management and community system. The system is a Drupal content management system based framework for managing different micro-contents, tutorial videos, lecture notes, tags etc. The users can register and login to the system, upload image-, animated image-, Prezi- or Youtube video-based micro-contents with the extended type of metadata such as title, description, tags: target audience, level, profession group, NVQ qualification. The teachers can evaluate the work of the students. Also, the students can rate the work of each other. This site collects all "digital free-hand" micro-contents. It means that a lot of users create valuable content units without any frameworks just using content authoring program (e.g. Power Point, Impress, Prezi). Digital diversity makes it difficult for computer-supported content analysis, but these are stacked for human use and classified as possible. The Drupal framework also helped us to optimize the screen for compact displays. Some integrated code snippets support to open the Youtube videos and the lecture notes with the application, and it is also possible to use the picture taken by the camera of the smartphone as the basis of different newly created micro-contents.

Fig. 8. OCD Micro-content management and community system.

Our achieved result is a native (Java-based), expandable Android application (Fig. 8) with which the different users, students and teachers of the Open Content Development Research Group and Partners and also the students from at least two faculties at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics can reach, use and create their learning units, the micro-contents on their smartphones.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

According to the current procedural approach, applying such solutions at the level of open content development requires decisions at the institutional level. Utilizing the advantages of digital transformation and the fact that it allows accessibility in space and time, comfort and personal time management in acquiring the learning material, we succeeded to open the process of content development and make it possible for teachers and students to share new knowledge by collaborative work.

This project encouraged the faculties of an institution to „learn” in an environment where information exchange organised into an informal network supported by IT devices has an increasingly important role. The point of the concept was formulating active student’s contribution as participation in the network and access to information as well as to the software packages were able to interpret data in various contexts, promoting cooperating and self-organised learning. This network concept, as the feature of active student’s contribution, encouraged the new educational content development. The result of these activities integrated an original model of OCD (open content development) to formulate a real open environment where information exchange is organised into an informal network. The result demonstrates the tested concept of students’ participation in the network and access to the micro-learning content packages that help to interpret information in various contexts.

According to the perspectives, the implementation of the OCD concept in engineering and teacher education has shown positive results based on first experiences. The new methodological process can be effectively integrated into teacher training as well as in teacher training. Based on the experience so far, the greatest achievement is the significant increase in teacher and student activity in content development, which is a significant innovation factor for the modernization and improvement of the rapidly changing educational content.

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5 REFERENCES

- [1] Gessler, M, Herrera M,L.(eds.), (2015) Special Edition: Vocational Didactics, *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 152-160.
- [2] Colons, A.; Halverson, R. (2009), *Rethinking Education in the Age of Technology*. Teacher College Press, New York.
- [3] Benedek, A. (2017), Visual Learning and Open Content Development, In: Benedek Andras, Veszelszki Agnes (Eds.) *Virtual Reality – Real Visuality: Virtual, Visual, Veridical*. 198 p. Frankfurt am Main; New York; Berlin; Bern; Bruxelles; New York; Oxford; Wien: Peter Lang GmbH, Internationaler Verlag der Wissenschaften, 2017. pp. 91-100. (Series Visual Learning; 7.) (ISBN:978-3-631-73104-8)
- [4] Benedek, A.; Molnár, Gy. (2014). *ICT in Education: A New paradigm and old obstacle* In: Arno Leist, Tadeusz Pankowski (eds.) ICCGI 2014: The Ninth International Multi-Conference on Computing in the Global Information Technology. Sevilla, Spain, 2014.06.22-IARIA. 54-60.
- [5] Benedek, A.; Molnár, Gy. (2015). *New Approaches to the E-content and E-textbook in Higher Education*, In: L Gómez Chova, A López Martínez, I Candel Torres (eds.), INTED2015 Proceedings: 9th International Technology, Education and Development Conference. Madrid, Spain, : International Academy of Technology, Education and Development (IATED), 2015. 3646-3650.
- [6] Beetham, H. and Sharpe, R. (ed.) (2013). *Rethinking Pedagogy for a Digital Age: Designing for 21st-century learning* (2nd edition). Abingdon: Routledge. See more: <http://www.dtransform.eu/>

[7] Nore, H. (2015) Re-Contextualizing Vocational Didactics in Norwegian Vocational Education and Training. *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training*, (IJRVET) Vol. 2, No. 3 (Special Issue), pp. 182-194.

[8] Vamos, T., Bars, R., Sik, D. (2016): Bird's Eye View on Systems and Control - General View and Case Studies, *IFAC Papersonline* 49 :pp. 274-279.

[9] Smartphone Market Share (2018): <https://www.idc.com/promo/smartphone-market-share/os>

(W1) <http://www.openculture.com/>
<https://en.unesco.org/themes/building-knowledge-societies/oer>
<https://er.educause.edu/articles/2017/3/transforming-our-libraries-from-analog-to-digital-a-2020-vision>

(W2) <http://sysbook.sztaki.hu/>

(W3) <http://sysbook.sztaki.hu/studentarea.php>

(W4) www.mikropedia.hu